

The need for an “ethics-and-research security-by-design” approach

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Abstract

Responsible design and use of Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems is a priority area for our societies, which should be based on ethical and human-centric principles, legal and human-rights frameworks. Numerous challenges emerge in the constantly evolving research environment: inherent ethical challenges associated with the technology itself,¹ emerging ethico-legal challenges associated with research practices,² and research security risks associated with the undesirable transfer of critical knowledge/technology, foreign interference and dual use.³ Thus, there is an urgent need to integrate ethics and research security practices in the research design and implementation.

The EU-funded project CHANGER⁴ aims to address research challenges by strengthening the researchers’ capacities to incorporate ethical judgements in the project design and implementation, and support Research Ethics Committees (RECs). We propose the adoption of an integrated “**ethics-and-research security-by-design**” approach for AI-related research, and develop tools to ensure that ethical principles and research security aspects are reflected, identified, and assessed before adjusting research activities accordingly:

1. The **ethics assessment methodology for AI** is a multi-level approach, integrating ethical reflections, socio-technical implications and emerging concerns regarding values and human rights, as well as legal and research security perspectives across the lifecycle of AI systems.
2. The **benchmarking tool for AI** is intended for RECs to assess their capacity to address the ever-increasing challenges posed by AI, considering also research security issues.

By incorporating ethical principles and research security measures in the research design, this approach aims to foster responsible innovation practices within the research ecosystem, aligned with the “legal-by-design” requirements (e.g. AI Act, GDPR, Council of Europe Framework Convention on AI).

¹ i.e. bias, discrimination, data protection, privacy, explainability, human rights violations.

² E.g. identifying human action in text/image production by Generative AI and intellectual property rights.

³ Council Recommendation on enhancing research security

<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/05/23/council-adopts-a-recommendation-to-enhance-research-security/> May 2024.

⁴ CHallenges and innovative chaNGes in research Ethics Reviews (CHANGER) EU-funded project.

<https://changer-project.eu/>